

KEY INDICATORS

With 604,803 hectares, Czechia ranked third among the EU-13 countries of the European Union in 2024 (after Romania and Poland). Also in terms of organic area share, it was the number two EU-13 country (17.2% of total farmland), following Estonia. Growth from 2001 to 2024 was at 177.7%, thus lower than in the EU. Organic retail sales amounted to 295.2 million euros, or 1.6% of all retail sales.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

217,869 ha (5.1%)

604,803 ha (17.2%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

177.7%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

90,797 ha (3.7%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

3,837 ha (8.7%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

410,447 ha (41.5%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

4 †

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

654 (1.3%)

5,567 (19.3%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

13

Processors

75

951

Importers

N/D

326

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

295.2 M€ (1.6%)

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

27.1 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

N/D

Imports

N/D

23,315 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN CZECHIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on UZEI, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN CZECHIA

Source: UZEI

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Czechia CAP Strategic Plan foresees an almost 50% increase in the supported organic area, increasing to 21% of UAA with almost all certified organic land receiving support. Payment rates per ha for arable land have been increased most, also with a clear differential for conversion support, reflecting a desire to increase the proportion of arable land managed organically, as most of the current organic land is permanent grassland. Nearly 17% of environmental support, and almost 6% of total CAP expenditure is planned to be allocated to organic farming in 2023-2027. In 2024, payments for arable and horticulture were increased, with highest increases for small growers <6ha. Payments were also increased for vineyards with greening between rows.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	506 kha	750 kha (+48%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	14.4%	21.3% (+48%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	97%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	53 M€	105 M€ (+98%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	105 €	140 € (+34%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	452 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	1,235 M€	16.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,478 M€	5.7%
Total CAP Expenditure	7,955 M€	

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	106	323	660	896	900
	2024	P2	106	343	780	896	900
Change from 2023 to 2024			0%	+6%	+18%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	100	230	638	850	847
	2024	P2	100	246	760	850	847
Change from 2023 to 2024			0%	+7%	+19%	0%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023		6%	40%	3%	5%	6%
	2024		6%	39%	3%	5%	6%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Czechia is now on its fourth national organic action plan since the first one in 2004. The current plan, like the previous one, has a strong focus on information initiatives for consumers and farmers, including training and research. A particular focus is the aim to increase the arable area under organic management, given the high area of grassland already converted.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET*	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2016-20	15% of UAA by 2020, of which 20% arable	3% of market by 2020
Current Action Plan	2021-27	22% of UAA by 2027, of which 30% arable	4% of market by 2027, 5% of public procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2016 - 2020)

PRODUCTION
 Increase domestic production and improve financial viability, esp. in environmentally sensitive areas

MARKETS
 Improve marketing; priority access to RDP support; improve supply chain conditions; reduce consumer prices; increase sales through public catering and gastronomy; introduce national logo; monitor use of GMOs in EU, maintain organic GMO prohibition

INFORMATION
 Increase consumption through promotion; awareness and trust building; information on environmental and other benefits; ensure organic farmers have access to information, advice comparable to non-organic; research dissemination, demonstration farms; use of RDP resources for training; include organic principles in school, college courses; increase research funding; co-ordinate research strategy; policy support evaluations; market data incl consumer attitudes

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2021 - 2027)

PRODUCTION
 Maintain support, encourage more arable, permanent crops, esp. in environmentally sensitive areas

MARKETS
 Improve processing capacity for domestic products; support for producer organisations; increase vertical integration and co-operation in supply chains; increase share of public catering; support training for catering staff; mandatory use of CZ logo on products processed in CZ

INFORMATION
 Increase consumption through promotion; increase trust and address price and accessibility concerns; support for advice, if possible free-of-charge, incl marketing, financial and conversion aspects; communicate research results in schools and higher education; technical training courses; online information portal; increase share of research funding to reflect share of land area, incl focus on animal welfare and environmental issues; improve statistical data collection

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Czechia is negligible. Czechia was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Organic aquaculture is not highlighted in the current organic action plan from 2021. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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